

Supplementary Figure S1. A-C) Plasma glucose, non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA), and BHB concentrations around dry-off in primiparous cows vaccinated 2 (CON-PRIM, n = 23) or 11 d before dry-off (EV-PRIM, n = 23). **D-F)** Plasma glucose, NEFA, and BHB concentrations around dry-off in multiparous cows vaccinated 2 (CON-MULT, n = 15) or 11 d before dry-off (EV-MULT, n = 15). **BL:** baseline samples (collected before vaccination on 11 d prior to dry-off). Data were analyzed using PROC MIXED procedure of SAS with repeated measures on days relative to dry-off. The statistical model included the fixed effects of treatment (CON vs. EV), day, and treatment by day interaction with cow nested within the treatment as the random effect. †: $0.05 \leq P < 0.10$. Error bars represent SEM.

